

Complex Formation between Vanadic Acid (V^{5+}) and Tartaric Acid

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Vanadic acid forms a red-coloured complex with tartaric acid. The formation is not instantaneous, but requires a certain interval of time. The formation up to the stable state as well as the composition of the complex at the stable state has been studied spectrophotometrically in the visible region. The complex has a maximum absorption at 480 m μ . Job's method¹ of continued variation has been adopted and a 2:1 complex as vanadic : tartaric acid has been observed. Measurements of *pH* also support this conclusion. The stability constant and the free energy change have been calculated and found to be 1.30×10^3 and -6.83 kcal./mole respectively at 25°.

Complex formation between metallic acid oxides and hydroxy compounds including α -hydroxy acids is well known². In recent years studies involving metallic acids, viz., arsenious and arsenic acids, molybdic, tungstic, antimonie, and germanic acids etc., prepared by ion-exchange method, have been carried out mainly by Richardson³, Gato and Richardson⁴, and Clark⁵ from conductivity and *pH* measurements. Complex formations between vanadyl ion and oxalic acid⁶ and citric acid⁷, respectively, have been studied by different workers. The reaction between vanadyl sulphate and Rochelle salt has been studied by spectrophotometric and conductometric methods by Bhattacharjee *et al.*⁸ From polarographic characteristics, Lingane⁹ and Meites¹⁰ have presented evidence for the existence of complexes of vanadium at different oxidation states with several complexing agents, including tetravalent vanadium ion with tartrate, citrate, and oxalate ions respectively. In the present communication, the complex formation between vanadic acid (V^{5+}), prepared by using ion-exchange method, and tartaric acid has been investigated by spectrophotometric and *pH*-metric measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials employed were of the highest purity available. Tartaric acid employed was (G. R.) E. Merck's product and ammonium metavanadate was of A. R. quality.

1. *Ann. chim.*, 1028, x, 9, 113.
2. Britton, "Hydrogen Ion", Vol. II, 1936, pp. 166-174.
3. *J. Inorg. & Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 273. 1960, 13, 84.
4. *Ibid.*, 1961, 23, 257, 265.
5. *Ibid.*, 1962, 24, 81.
6. Zolotavin and Kalugina, *Zhur. Obshch. Khim.*, 1956, 27, 1355.
7. *Idem*, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1950, 1, 703.
8. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 240.
9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 182.
10. *Ibid.*, 1947, 69, 1021, 1882.

Both were dissolved in double distilled water and stored in Jena bottles. The standardisation of tartaric acid was effected against standard alkali.

Preparation and Estimation of Vanadic Acid.—In a tall and fairly wide pyrex tube, a sufficient amount of a strong hydrogen-ion exchange resin, Amberlite-I.R.120, analytical grade of Rohm & Haas Company, Pennsylvania, was taken and washed repeatedly with conductivity water until the percolated water attained the conductivity of the original water. The required amount of ammonium metavanadate solution, previously filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 40, was then percolated through the resin at a slow rate (2 drops/sec.), the amount percolated being one third of the total exchange capacity of the resin (15g. resin = 30 ml of *N*-alkali) to ensure complete conversion. The clear yellow solution of vanadic acid, thus obtained, was stored in a Jena bottle. A known amount of the acid, analysed by Kjeldahl's method, indicated absence of ammonia. The V_2O_5 content of this acid solution was estimated by evaporation and drying to a constant weight. By adjusting the strength of the metavanadate solution and the time of percolation, vanadic acid, almost of the same strength, can be prepared each time.

For measuring the absorption of light a Beckman spectrophotometer (Model D.U.) and glass cells of path length 1 cm were used. The pH measurements were carried out in a Cambridge Bench Type pH-meter, calibrated before use with standard buffers.

Formation of the Complex.—The formation of the complex was not instantaneous, but took place slowly. The complex remained stable for about half an hour and then started decomposing. This was noted from the increase of the optical density at wave length 480 μ for five different mixtures containing 4:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4 as ratios between vanadic acid and tartaric acid respectively with time. The data are represented in Fig. 1 up to the stage of constant attainment of the optical density.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

⊙ (Curve 1) and ● (curve 2) are points for vanadic and the complex with water as control (ratio=2:1 :: V:TA).

⊗ (Curve 3) and ●' (curve 4) are points for vanadic and the complex with water as control (ratio=1:1 :: V:TA).

Absorption Spectra of Vanadic Acid.—Absorption spectra were studied in the visible region. Two solutions were made of vanadic acid and tartaric acid in the ratios of 2:1 and 1:1. Another two samples containing the same concentration of vanadic acid were prepared and their spectra measured, using water as blank. Fig. 2 represents the spectra of vanadic acid of two concentrations, namely 0.017*M* and 0.0125*M*, and that of the complex at the stable state containing vanadic acid of the aforesaid strengths respectively. No sharp maximum in the case of complex was noticeable.

FIG. 3

1—For V: TA=2:1, ⊙ expt. points with vanadic acid as control; ×—calc. points.
 2—For V: TA=1:1, ● expt. points with vanadic acid as control; △—calc. points.

Mole fraction of TA.

FIG. 4

Stoichiometry of the Complex

(a). *From Optical Density Measurements.*—The composition of the complex was determined by using Job's method¹ of continued variation. Equimolecular solutions (0.011*M* and 0.005*M*) of vanadic acid and tartaric acid were mixed in different molecular ratios, keeping the total volume always constant; their optical densities at the steady state were measured in the spectrophotometer. The wave lengths of light used were 480 mμ, 500 mμ, and 520 mμ. Since the vanadic acid possesses definite accountable absorption at these wave lengths, the difference in the optical density of the complex and the vanadic acid have been plotted against the mole fraction of tartaric acid. At all wave lengths the peaks are found to occur at vanadic acid to tartaric acid ratio as 2:1. This will be evident from Fig. 5.

(b). *From pH Measurements.*—The complex acid formed by the reaction of vanadic acid with tartaric acid is expected to be a stronger one than the reactants and hence pH should diminish. Equimolecular solutions of vanadic acid and tartaric acid of concentration 0.019 *M* were mixed in different proportions. Keeping the total volume always constant, the pH of each mixture was measured at the steady state. The values of pH have then been plotted against the mole fractions of tartaric acid (Fig. 4). The minimum pH is found at 2:1 ratio of vanadic acid: tartaric acid which is evidently the composition of the complex.

Extinction Coefficients of the Vanadic Acid and of the Complex.—Beer's law was found to hold good for solutions of vanadic acid and its complex over a wide range of wave lengths. The extinction coefficients were found out by measuring optical densities at wave lengths

480 μ and 500 μ for different concentrations and by plotting the respective optical densities against concentrations. The data are represented in Fig. 6. In the case of the complex the ligand was always kept in large excess in order to achieve more or less complete complex formation, so that the optical density might correspond to the optical density of the complex only. The molar extinction coefficients, as found from the slopes of the graphs, are 69 and 23 for vanadic acid at 380 μ and 500 μ respectively. The corresponding molar extinction coefficients of the complex are found to be 1250 and 950 respectively.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

1-2. Complex at 480 and 500 μ (R.S. scale);
3-4. Vanadic acid at 480 and 500 μ (L.S. scale).

DISCUSSION

Formation of the complex has been indicated in Fig. 1 in which curves 1-5 refer respectively to vanadic acid: tartaric acid ratio as 4:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4. The curves of the complex (Fig. 2) show tendency to become flat near about 460 μ and 480 μ , whereas those of vanadic acid are exponential. When the difference in optical densities at each of the wave lengths used is plotted against wave length, a curve having maximum at 480 μ is obtained. This is illustrated in Fig. 3 (curves through $\times$ and Δ points). Using vanadic acid of the same concentration as is present in the complex, instead of water as a blank, similar curves having maxima at 480 μ have been obtained (vide Fig. 3, curves through $\odot$ and $\bullet$ points).

It appears from these curves that the experimental and calculated points fall very

close to each other. The observation of maxima at 480 m μ only, for two different vanadic acid—tartaric acid ratios, supports the presence of only one complex in the system.

For elucidation of the composition of the complex, both spectrophotometric and *pH*-metric methods have been adopted. The concentrations of vanadic acid used are 0.011*M* and 0.005*M* and the wave lengths of light used are 480 m μ , 500 m μ , and 520 m μ . At all these wave lengths peaks occurred at a vanadic acid: tartaric acid ratio of 2:1 (vide Fig. 5). From the *pH* curve, represented in Fig. 4, it is evident that at 2:1 ratio the lowest *pH* is obtained, confirming the existence of a strong complex acid. In the case of antimonic acid and α -hydroxy-acids, Gate and Richardson¹¹ have also made a similar observation. Both these methods thus indicate the formation of a complex resulting from the interaction of vanadic acid and tartaric acid. From conductivity measurements also, existence of a 2:1 complex has been reported by us. For the structure of the complex acid we refer to our recent publication¹¹.

Stability Constant of the Complex Acid

The extinction coefficients of the vanadic acid and the complex at 480 m μ and 500 m μ have been found to be 68 and 23 and 1200 and 940 respectively. These values have been utilised in calculating the stability constant of the complex. The method of calculation is given below.

At any vanadic acid-tartaric ratio, the total optical density at any wave length of light

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{O.D. of vanadic acid free} + \text{O.D. of complex} \\ &= \text{O.D. of total vanadic acid} - \text{O.D. of vanadic acid in complex} + \text{O.D. of complex} \\ &= [\text{total vanadic acid}] \epsilon - 2 \epsilon [\text{complex}] + \epsilon' [\text{complex}] \\ &= [\text{total vanadic acid}] \epsilon - (2\epsilon - \epsilon') [\text{complex}] \end{aligned}$$

where, ϵ and ϵ' are the extinction coefficients of the vanadic acid and the complex respectively.

From this relation the concentration of the complex can be calculated if the optical density of the mixture is known. In this way the concentrations of the complex at 2:1 ratio for 480 m μ and 500 m μ have been calculated.

For the stability constant, the following equilibrium has then been considered:

$$\therefore K(\text{equilibrium constant}) = \frac{[c]}{[(a-2c)]^2[(b-c)]}$$

The equilibrium constants have been calculated from the above equation for mixtures having constituents in different proportions near the maximum optical density. These are shown in Table I.

11. Mullick, Moulik and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 137.

TABLE I

Wave length.	Concentration.		<i>K</i> .	Mean <i>K</i> .
	Vannalic acid.	Tartaric acid.		
480 mμ	0.0033 <i>M</i>	0.0017 <i>M</i>	8.0×10^4	
"	0.0025	0.0025	5.2	
500	0.0077	0.0039	9.0	7.35×10^4
"	0.0057	0.0057	7.2	

The average of these values, 7.35×10^4 , has been considered as the equilibrium constant. The dissociation constant (reciprocal of equilibrium constant) has been calculated and a value of 1.36×10^{-3} obtained. The value of the equilibrium constant has been used in calculating the free energy,

$$-\Delta F = RT \ln K,$$

and a value of 6.83 kcal./mole has been obtained.

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